

DESIGN ANALYSIS OF STRUCTURAL STEEL AND CARBON FIBER LEAF SPRING

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Abstract

The objective within the automotive sector is to decrease weight of the leaf spring. This weight reduction can be achieved through the integration of advanced materials, optimized designs, and enhanced manufacturing practices. The industry has demonstrated considerable enthusiasm for replacing conventional steel leaf springs with those made from composites, due to their superior strength-to-weight ratio and enhanced capacity for strain energy storage. Research into the utilization of carbon fiber materials allows for a reduction in spring weight while preserving load-bearing strength. The selection of material depends on factors such as purpose of utilization, material properties, expense and durability. The ongoing project aspires to design, analyze, and produce a carbon fiber reinforced plastic leaf spring tailored for light motor vehicles, aiming to achieve a spring that is as lightweight as possible while enduring specified external static forces without failure.

Keywords: Carbon fiber leaf spring, Composite leaf spring, Steel leaf spring, Boundary conditions.

1. Introduction

The automotive industry necessitates large amounts of metals and alloys to produce various vehicle parts. The notion of replacing metals appeared unrealistic. However, rapid progress in materials such as glass, polymers, ceramics, synthetic fibers, and specific organic and inorganic compounds has signified a crucial shift. What's particularly intriguing is that by combining two or more materials, one can attain improved mechanical properties. Composites feature exceptional qualities like high specific strength, stiffness, and durability. Due to these traits, composites are employed in a wide range of applications, not only for their attributes but also for their lightweight and cost-efficiency. A prominent example is the composite leaf spring. Leaf springs primarily function in suspension systems to reduce shock loads in vehicles, which include light cars, heavy trucks, and rail systems. They withstand lateral forces, braking torque, and driving torque while also absorbing impacts. A significant advantage of a leaf spring compared to a helical spring is that the ends can be directed along a specific path as they bend, enabling them to operate as both a structural element and an energy-absorbing mechanism. Studies suggest that a material with maximum. Sports vehicles like the Mahindra incorporate leaf springs at the rear axle. Numerous researchers have experimented with different composite materials to replace existing conventional leaf springs, effectively minimizing weight and overall

expenditures while maintaining the load-bearing capacity, strength and other properties of the materials. Many employed various optimization methods to discover the most fitting alternatives to the existing materials.

Currently, significant research efforts are underway to substitute conventional leaf springs with composite materials. Various authors have concentrated on different fiber-reinforced composites, highlighting their extensive benefits over steel alternatives. This research paper provides a concise overview of carbon fiber-reinforced composites used for leaf spring.

1.1 Composite Materials as a Replacement for Steel Leaf Springs

Following are the different types of composite materials used for manufacturing of leaf spring.

1.1.1 Synthetic Fiber-Based Reinforced Composites

Including carbon, graphite, glass, and Kevlar, in conjunction with suitable resins, are primarily utilized as composite materials due to their exceptional characteristics such as a high strength-to-weight ratio and impressive modulus to density. A comparative analysis between steel and composite leaf springs has been conducted, taking into account strength, weight, and expense. A glass fiber-reinforced composite with varying thickness and width was conceptualized and crafted using a simple hand lay-up technique.

1.1.2 Natural Fiber-Based Reinforced Composites

In light of cost considerations and resource conservation in the current situation, many researchers have sought to replace synthetic fibers with natural alternatives for enhanced outcomes. These materials are biodegradable, renewable, recyclable, eco-friendly, and generally more affordable than synthetic fibers. Various natural fibers, including jute, sisal, flax, coir, and bamboo, are employed for automotive, sporting, and structural applications. The proportions of epoxy, E-glass, and silk are pivotal in the design, analysis, and fabrication of natural fiber-reinforced composites.

1.1.3 Hybrid (Synthetic/Natural) Composites

The design and fabrication of a hybrid composite (preferably reinforced with glass/carbon) leaf spring for vehicles, which demonstrated a sufficiently high natural frequency to avoid resonance, were carried out. The natural frequencies of mono steel leaf springs and hybrid composites were compiled. In this structure, carbon fibers are positioned in the outer layers to enhance load-bearing capability while glass fibers are situated in the inner layers for improved damping. An analysis conducted using ANSYS indicated that the hybrid laminate can endure maximum loads while generating lower stresses.

1.2 Material selection:

For conventional materials, SUP9 chosen which standard material is with their properties detailed in below table.

Table 1: Properties of Conventional Material

Properties of SUP9	Value
Young's Modulus (Mpa)	2.1E+5
Tensile Strength (N/mm ²)	1962
Density (kg/mm ³)	7850
Poisson Ratio	0.27

In contrast to conventional materials, carbon fibers material selected as a compositematerial due to their improved strength and their properties detailed in below table.

Table 2: Properties of carbon fiber

Properties of carbon fiber	Value
Tensile modulus (GPa)	294
Tensile strength (MPa)	5880
Density (g/cm ³)	1.8
Major Poisson's ratio	0.28

Carbon fiber, as the name suggests, is a fiber crafted from carbon. However, these fibers serve merely as a foundation. The term 'carbon fiber' typically refers to a material made up of extremely fine strands of carbon atoms. When these strands are combined with plastic polymer resin through heat, pressure, or in a vacuum, a composite material emerges that is both robust and lightweight. Historically, steel and other durable construction materials have transformed the industrial landscape. Today, we find ourselves at a juncture where a superior material is required to meet the escalating demands of contemporary society. This necessity has ushered in a modern material known as carbon fibers. Carbon fiber stands out as one of the most advanced reinforcement materials utilized in composites. It is a truly high-tech substance, boasting exceptional structural characteristics, surpassing those of any metal. The tensile strength of carbon fiber is nearly threefold that of steel, while being 4.5 times less dense. Carbon fibers exhibit Young's modulus values ranging from 150-300 GPa. The versatility of carbon fiber material offers a broad spectrum of applications, as it can be shaped into various densities and an infinite array of shapes and sizes. Carbon fiber is often moulded into tubing, fabrics, and cloth, and can be customized into countless composite components and parts. This extraordinarily valuable material employed in composites is expected to maintain an upward trajectory in the manufacturing market share. As more cost-effective methods for producing carbon fiber composites are discovered, prices are likely to decrease, enabling more industries to leverage this extraordinary material.

The strength of a material is defined as the force exerted per unit area at the point of failure, divided by its density. Any material that is both strong and light possesses a favourable Strength/Weight ratio. Carbon Fiber features a high Strength to Weight Ratio.

2. Problem Statement

At present, various sectors within the automotive industry face a significant challenge in minimizing vehicle weight while preserving natural resources and utilizing energy efficiently. To reach this goal, they are concentrating on substituting current materials with innovative, advanced, and lightweight alternatives. In today's context, there is an increasing demand for composite materials. These materials feature numerous important applications alongside their remarkable attributes, such as high strength, rigidity, excellent wear and corrosion resistance, low density, and exceptional fracture toughness. Given that the suspension system comprises (upto 20%) of the unsprung weight in a vehicle, it necessitates an upgrade to a lighter option.

3. Objective

To create 3D CAD model using CATIA V5 and conduct FEA analysis through ANSYS Workbench on the leaf spring under static loading conditions.

To design carbon fiber composite leaf springs for light motor vehicles.

The aim of this research is to evaluate the properties of carbon fiber composite leaf springs in comparison to conventional steel leaf springs.

4. Design calculation

In the pursuit of our study focusing on light motor vehicles, we will examine the Maruti Suzuki Alto 800, which possesses a weight ranging from approximately 735 to 850 Kg.

Vehicle Weight = 850 Kg

Max Load Capacity = 535 Kg

Gross Vehicle Weight (W) = 850 + 535 = 1385 Kg
= 13850N

Given vehicle is a four-wheeler, one leaf spring allocated to one wheel manages a quarter of the total weight.
Weight manage per leaf spring = $13850/4 = 3462.5$ N

4.1 CAD

Computer-aided design (CAD) refers to employing computer systems (or workstations) to assist in crafting, modifying, analyzing, or enhancing a design. CAD software aims to boost the designer's productivity, elevate design quality, facilitate communication through documentation, and establish a manufacturing database. The result from CAD is commonly electronic files used for printing, machining, or various manufacturing tasks. The acronym CADD (for Computer Aided Design and Drafting) is also applied. Its application in the development of electronic systems is termed electronic design automation (EDA). In the realm of mechanical design, it is referred to as mechanical design automation (MDA) or computer-aided drafting (CAD), encompassing the process of generating a technical drawing using computer software

Figure 1: CATIA of Steel Mono-Leaf Spring

4.2 Finite Element Analysis

4.2.1 Overview of Finite Element Analysis

Finite element analysis (FEA) serves as an analytical strategy for addressing practical challenges in engineering contexts. Initially, these challenges are transformed into matrix and partial differential equation representations. Ultimately, these partial differential and integral equations are solved to derive a solution to the posed problem. The sheer volume of equations involved typically renders a solution by manual means unfeasible, establishing the necessity for various FEA software packages. Numerous FEA tools exist to cater to diverse applications, among which Pro Mechanical, ANSYS, NASTRAN, and Gambit rank as highly regarded solutions.

In the realm of mathematics, finite element analysis (FEA) is recognized as a numerical method designed to

identify approximate solutions to boundary value dilemmas associated with partial differential equations. This approach involves partitioning the comprehensive problem domain into more manageable fragments known as finite elements, utilizing different techniques from calculus of variations to resolve the issue by minimizing a related error function. Much like the concept of approximating a larger circle by connecting numerous tiny straight lines, FEA employs methods for intertwining several elementary equations over small sub-regions, referred to as finite elements, in order to closely approximate a more intricate equation over an expansive domain.

Finite element analysis (FEA) is an invaluable and robust method for calculating stresses and strains within structures or components that are too elaborate for conventional analytical techniques. This methodology deconstructs the structure or component into numerous small segments (a finite count of elements) of various designs, dimensions, and configurations. It is presumed that the elements exhibit a simplified deformation pattern (linear, quadratic, etc.) and are linked at “nodes,” typically situated at corners or edges of the elements. These elements are then aggregated mathematically utilizing fundamental structural mechanics principles, such as force equilibrium and displacement continuity, resulting in a significant system of simultaneous equations. By employing computer resources to solve these extensive simultaneous equations, the deformed shape of the structure or component under applied loads is obtained. Subsequently, stresses and strains are computed. Finite element analysis (FEA) is arguably the most adaptable approach for assessing stress intensity factors. This method primarily involves determining displacements at nodal points of the body, which has been represented as a system of elements interconnected at these nodal points. FEA has emerged as a formidable resource for numerically addressing a broad spectrum of engineering challenges and has been extensively utilized to solve issues involving irregular areas and intricate models.

4.2.2 Phases of Finite Element Analysis

The application of FEA to engineering challenges, such as calculating deflections and stresses in a structure, necessitates three fundamental phases:

Phase1: Pre-processing

Phase2: Solution

Phase3: Post-processing

A brief overview of each phase follows.

Phase 1: Pre-processing

Employing a CAD application, provided either by the FEA software or via external 3D CAD modeling tools such as Pro-E, Catia, and Solid Edge, the structure is designed. The finalized FEA model comprises multiple elements that together depict the entirety of the structure. These elements not only signify fragments of the structure but also emulate its mechanical characteristics and behavior.

Regions with complex geometries (such as curves, notches, and holes) necessitate a greater number of elements for accurate shape representation, whereas areas with simpler geometries can be modeled using a coarser mesh (or fewer elements). The selection of appropriate elements requires previous experience with FEA, understanding the structure’s behavior, knowledge of the available elements within the software, and their attributes. The elements connect at the nodes, or shared points. During the pre-processing phase, in addition to the structure's geometry, constraints, loads, and mechanical properties are defined. Thus, the entire structure is comprehensively defined through the geometric model in the pre-processing stage. The structure defined by nodes and elements is referred to as a “mesh.”

Phase 2: Solution

In this phase, the geometry, constraints, mechanical properties, and loads are applied to formulate matrix equations for each element, which are then integrated to create a global matrix equation for the structure. The form of both the individual and structural equations remains:

$$\{F\} = [K] \{u\} \quad (1)$$

Where

{F} = External force matrix,

[K] = Global stiffness matrix,

{u} = Displacement matrix.

This equation is then resolved for deflections. Utilizing the obtained deflection values, strain, stress, and reactions are computed. All results are recorded and can subsequently be utilized to produce graphical representations and charts during post-analysis

Phase 3: Post-processing

This marks the concluding phase of a finite element evaluation. The outcomes derived in step 2 typically manifest as unrefined data, making them challenging to comprehend. During the post-analysis phase, a CAD application is employed to adjust the data to produce the deflected shape of the structure, generate stress visualizations, animations, and more. A visual depiction of the findings is immensely beneficial for grasping the structure's behaviour.

4.3 Steps of Finite Element Method (FEM)

In the current study, ANSYS (Analysis System) software is utilized for the analysis. Essentially, it employs the Finite Element Method (FEM) to address any issue. The following are the steps in detail:

Step 1: Geometry

Step 2: Meshing

Step 3: Boundary condition

Step 4: Solve (Solution)

Step 5: Interpretation of Results

Details are as follows

4.3.1 Geometry

The Workbench encompasses various types of analyses, including static, modal, harmonic, explicit dynamics, CFD, ACP tool post, CFX, topology optimization, etc., tailored to the defined problem.

Figure 2: Geometry

Specifications for materials such as copper, steel, grey cast iron, composite materials, and fluid domain materials are established in the engineering data. For instance, the default material in ANSYS is structural steel.

Geometry created using any CAD software, including CATIA, PRO E, SOLIDWORKS, INVENTOR, etc., is imported in the geometry section. If any modifications are necessary, they can be executed in the geometry section of Design Modeler or Space Claim.

After importing the component in the model section, Material is allocated to the component in accordance with the existing material.

The connections are verified in the contact region, such as bonded, frictionless, and frictional, no separation, etc., for multi-body components. Meshing is carried out to segment components into smaller pieces (elements) based on size, with tetrahedral mesh and hexahedral mesh preferred for 3D geometries, while quadrilateral or triangular meshes are generally chosen for 2D geometries.

Boundary conditions are imposed based on the analysis, including fixed support, pressure, force, displacement, and velocity according to the requirements.

The problem is now clearly defined, and the solve option is chosen to acquire the solution in terms of equivalent stress, strain, energy, reaction force, etc.

ANSYS Workbench 21.0 serves as the platform to conduct modal analysis on thrust coupling. As the most sophisticated CAE software, ANSYS Workbench 21.0 offers users simulation modules across various domains, including structure, fluid, electromagnetic, heat transfer, and more. It stands as the industry's pinnacle of engineering simulation technology integration, featuring an intuitive and user-friendly interface, along with convenient pre-processing and post-processing functionalities and its vast solution capabilities.

Figure 3: Material Properties of Structural Steel

Properties of Outline Row 3: Structural Steel			
	A	B	C
1	Property	Value	Unit
2	Material Field Variables	Table	
3	Density	7850	kg m ⁻³
4	Isotropic Secant Coefficient of Thermal Expansion		
6	Isotropic Elasticity		
7	Derive from	Young's Modu...	
8	Young's Modulus	2E+11	Pa
9	Poisson's Ratio	0.3	
10	Bulk Modulus	1.6667E+11	Pa
11	Shear Modulus	7.6923E+10	Pa

Properties	
☐ Volume	8.1065e+005 mm ³
☐ Mass	6.3636 kg

4.3.2 Meshing

ANSYS Meshing is a versatile, intelligent, and automated high-performance tool designed for general use. It crafts the most suitable mesh to ensure precise and efficient Multiphysics solutions. With just a single click, a mesh tailored for a specific analysis can be produced for all components in a model. For the seasoned user seeking to optimize the mesh, complete control over the generation options is provided. The robust capabilities of parallel processing are leveraged automatically to minimize the waiting time for mesh creation. Establishing the most fitting mesh is crucial for engineering simulations. ANSYS Meshing recognizes the types of solutions applicable to the project and employs the relevant criteria to develop the best-adapted mesh. It seamlessly integrates with each solver in the ANSYS Workbench environment. For quick analyses or for new and occasional users, a functional mesh can be generated with just one click. ANSYS Meshing selects the most suitable options based on the analysis type and the model's geometry. Notably, ANSYS Meshing has the capability to utilize the available cores on the computer for parallel processing, significantly expediting mesh creation. Parallel meshing is provided at no extra cost or licensing requirements.

The final model of the 4-wheeler Steel Leaf Spring consists of 26,613 nodes and 4,464 elements, with an element size of 10 mm.

Figure 4: Meshing of Structural Steel Leaf Spring

4.3.3 Element Categories

When dealing with intricate geometries or significant variations in flow length scales, a triangular/tetrahedral mesh can be constructed with considerably fewer cells than a comparable quadrilateral/hexahedral mesh would require. This advantage arises because triangular/tetrahedral meshes enable cell clustering in specific areas of the flow domain. Conversely, structured quadrilateral/hexahedral meshes tend to place cells in unnecessary regions. Unstructured quadrilateral/hexahedral meshes provide many benefits similar to triangular/tetrahedral meshes when faced with moderately complex geometries.

- For simple shapes, implement quadrilateral/hexahedral meshes.
- For moderately intricate shapes, implement unstructured quadrilateral/hexahedral meshes.
- For relatively complex shapes, apply triangular/tetrahedral meshes with prism layers.
- For highly intricate shapes, employ purely triangular/tetrahedral meshes.

4.3.4 Boundary Conditions

A boundary condition for the model involves assigning a known value for either displacement or an associated load. For any specific node, you can configure either the load or the displacement, but not both simultaneously. The primary types of loading options available in FEA comprise force, pressure, and temperature. These can be applied to points, surfaces, edges, nodes, and elements, or they can be offset remotely from certain features. Overly constrained or under-constrained models can yield stress calculations that are inaccurate to the point of being useless for engineers. Ideally, we could have vast assemblies of components interconnected by contact elements, but such an endeavour is often beyond the budget and resources of most. However, we can maximize the potential of the computing hardware at our disposal, which necessitates a comprehension of how to implement realistic boundary conditions.

Weight of Vehicle = 850 Kg
Maximum Load Carrying Capacity = 535 Kg
Total Weight = 850 + 535 = 1385 Kg
Total Weight = $W = 1385 \times 10 = 13850\text{N}$

Since the vehicle is a 4-wheeler a single leaf spring corresponding to one of the wheels takes up $\frac{1}{4}$ th of the total weight.
 $F = 13850/4 = 3462.5\text{ N}$

Figure 5: Boundary condition of Structural Steel Leaf Spring

4.4 Results

4.4.1 Total Deformation of steel leaf spring

After applying boundary conditions on steel leaf spring it is observed that maximum deformation is 1.3766 mm and minimum deformation is 00 mm.

Figure 6: Total Deformation of Structural Steel Leaf Spring

4.4.2 Equivalent Stress of steel leaf spring

After applying boundary conditions on steel leaf spring it is observed that maximum and minimum equivalent (von-Mises) stresses developed are 175.04 Mpa and 1.167e-6 respectively.

Figure 7: Equivalent Stress of Steel Leaf Spring

4.4.3 Maximum equivalent elastic strain of steel leaf spring

Calculated maximum equivalent elastic strain in steel leaf spring is 0.0008755.

Figure 8: Equivalent Elastic Strain of Steel Leaf Spring

4.5 Design analysis of Carbon Fiber Composite Leaf Spring

4.5.1 FEA of Carbon Fiber Composite Leaf Spring

Figure 9: Geometry of Carbon Fiber Leaf Spring

4.5.2 Material properties

Figure 10: Material Properties of Composite Carbon Fiber

Properties of Outline Row 5: Epoxy Carbon Woven (230 GPa) Wet			
	A	B	C
1	Property	Value	Unit
2	Density	1451	kg m ⁻³
3	Orthotropic Secant Coefficient of Thermal Expansion		
8	Orthotropic Elasticity		
9	Young's Modulus X direction	5.916E+10	Pa
10	Young's Modulus Y direction	5.916E+10	Pa
11	Young's Modulus Z direction	7.5E+09	Pa
12	Poisson's Ratio XY	0.04	
13	Poisson's Ratio YZ	0.3	
14	Poisson's Ratio XZ	0.3	
15	Shear Modulus XY	3.3E+09	Pa
16	Shear Modulus YZ	2.7E+09	Pa
17	Shear Modulus XZ	2.7E+09	Pa

Properties	
☐ Volume	8.1065e+005 mm ³
☐ Mass	1.4997 kg

4.5.3 Meshing

Figure 11: Meshing of Carbon Fiber composite Leaf Spring

4.5.4 Boundary condition

Figure 12: Boundary Condition on Carbon Fiber composite Leaf Spring

4.5.5 Total deformation

After applying boundary conditions on carbon fiber leaf spring it is observed that maximum deformation is 7.1935 mm and minimum deformation is 00 mm.

Figure 13: Total Deformation of carbon fiber composite leaf spring

4.5.6 Equivalent Stress

Boundary conditions apply on the on carbon fiber leaf spring and it is found that maximum and minimum equivalent (von-Mises) stresses developed are 194.00 Mpa and $1.08364e-7$ respectively.

Figure 14: Equivalent Stress of carbon fiber composite leaf spring

4.5.7 Equivalent Elastic Strain

Maximum and minimum equivalent elastic strain in carbon fiber leaf spring is 0.0082505 and $3.1894e-11$ respectively.

Figure 15: Equivalent Elastic Strain of carbon fiber composite leaf spring

4.5.8 Comparison of FEA Result:

Table 3: Comparison of FEA results of steel and CFRP leaf spring

Parameter	Steel Leaf Spring	Carbon Fibre leaf Spring
Weight (Kg)	6.36	1.449
Total Deformation (mm)	1.376	7.1935
Equivalent Stress (MPa)	175.04	194
Equivalent Strain	0.00087555	0.00825

5. Future Scope

In present work different technique will used for the manufacturing of CFRP leaf spring and experimental comparison has been made between composite leaf spring with steel leaf spring having same design and same load carrying capacity at component level.

In future to calculate fatigue life of composite leaf spring can lead to the dynamic analysis.

As the weight of the vehicle is reduced by applying composite leaf spring and the improvement in fuel efficiency of light motor vehicle can be calculated on different routes including city and highway.

Different manufacturing techniques can be used to increase the rate of production of composite leaf springs.

Sophisticated design of suspension can be prepare by using light weight composite leaf spring.

Composite leaf spring can be used for heavy duty vehicles also by improving the properties of composite material and changing its design parameters

Vehicle can prepare with latest technology and doing a modification in leaf spring to fulfil the customer's satisfactions related to the suspension system.

6. Conclusion

Comparison has been made between composite leaf spring with steel leaf spring having same design and same load carrying capacity.

The stress and displacements have been calculated using ANSYS for steel leaf spring and composite leaf spring. From the static analysis results it is found that there is a maximum displacement of 1.376 mm in the steel leaf spring and 7.1935 mm in carbon fiber leaf spring.

By analyzing the design, it was found that all the stresses in the leaf spring were well within the allowable limits and with good factor of safety.

The strength to weight ratio is higher for composite leaf spring than conventional steel spring with similar design.

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